

The K_1 and K_2 values have been evaluated from linear plots of the relation

$$\left(\frac{2-\bar{n}_h}{\bar{n}_h}\right)[H^+]^2 = -\frac{1}{K_2}\left(\frac{1-\bar{n}_h}{\bar{n}_h}\right)[H^+] + \frac{1}{K_1K_2} \quad \dots (21)$$

deduced from equations (15), (16) and (19). Results are stated in Table 1.

The $\bar{n}_h$ values have also been calculated using the experimentally determined values of K_1 and K_2 employing the relation

$$\bar{n}_h(\text{calc.}) = \frac{2K_1K_2[H^+]^2 + K_1[H^+]}{K_1K_2[H^+]^2 + K_1[H^+] + 1} \quad \dots (22)$$

and calculated acid association curves [$\bar{n}_h(\text{calc.})$ against pH] were drawn along with the experimental points (Figs. 1 and 2).

Discussion

As expected $R_6^4H_3$ has been found to be stronger acid than $R_6^6H_3$ indicated by pK^* values (Table 1) evidently due to the interpolation of one more methylene group in between two $-COOH$ groups in $R_6^6H_3$.

Proton dissociation constants of complex compounds such as $-SO_2HN \rightarrow M \leftarrow : NHO_2S-$ are related to the metal ligand stability constants. The stronger is the $M-N$ bond, the more easily dissociable is the proton bound to nitrogen. Acid association constants of the complex ions are therefore taken as a measure of instability of the complexes⁴, the stability order is $Hg(II) > Cu(II)$. The deviation of the experimental points from the calculated curves (Figs. 1 and 2) at the later stages of titrations i.e., at lower pH values, is due to the commencement of precipitation and/or decomposition of the complex compounds. For $Hg(II)$ complexes, the more basic is the ligand, the easier is the protonation of the complex ion. But regarding $Cu(II)$ complexes, no definite conclusion could be made as the protonation of the complex ion $Cu(R_6^6)_2^{4-}$ appears to be a complex one indicated by appreciable deviation of the experimental points from the calculated curve (Fig. 2) also at the earlier stages of titrations. Similar results have also been obtained for $Cu(R_6^6)_2^{4-}$ where titrations were made with HNO_3 using KNO_3 as the background electrolyte⁵.

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References

1. N. N. GHOSH and M. M. NANDI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 596.
2. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI and H. ROSSOTTI, "The Determination of Stability Constants and other Equilibrium Constants in Solution", McGraw-Hill Book & Co., London, 1961, p. 89.
3. S. G. HEDIN, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3197.
4. N. N. GHOSH and M. N. MAJUMDER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 559.
5. N. N. GHOSH and M. DASGUPTA, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1970, 375, 315.

Potential Antidiabetics: Bis-Benzimidazole-2-Sulphonamido Derivatives

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SYNTHALIN¹ is known as a compound with high hypoglycemic activity. The length of the carbon chain in the molecule which is $-(CH_2)_{10}-$ may be one of the factors which is responsible for such an activity². Carbutamide and tolbutamide also possess a marked hypoglycemic action which may be due to the sulphonamido group which each contains³. Urea 1,1'-ethylene bis-3-(*p*-tolylsulphonyl) and its analogues were tested for their hypoglycemic activity and was found that they lowered the blood sugar level when given orally⁴.

Okamoto and co-workers⁵ have reported that benzimidazole nucleus itself has high antidiabetic activity. An examination of the above facts together with the encouraging results we have obtained from benzimidazole derivatives⁶ with sulphonamido group substituted at position 2 of the benzimidazole nucleus prompted us to synthesise a new series of compounds represented by I containing benzimidazole nucleus, sulphonamido group and a varying long chain carbon linkage not examined so far for their antidiabetic property. It was thought that this would probably lead to compounds possessing greater antidiabetic activity.

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Experimental

Preparation of 2-benzimidazolesulphonyl chloride⁸:

2-mercapto benzimidazole⁷ 20 g in 800 ml of 20% ACOH was cooled in an ice bath and Cl_2 was passed first slowly and then vigorously for 50-55 min. The product was filtered quickly.

General method for the preparation of bis-benzimidazole-2-sulphonamide derivatives:

A mixture of 2 moles of the above sulphonyl chloride and 1 mole of the diamines in 20 ml of dry pyridine was refluxed for 3-4 hrs. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, the residue was washed with cold water and then recrystallised from water to give the compounds mentioned in Table 1.

Pharmacology:

The compounds were studied for their hypoglycemic action in albino rats of either sex weighing

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NOTES

TABLE 1

No. of compounds	<i>n</i> as in 1	C		H		N		M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula
		Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %	Found %			
1.	2	45.7	45.5	3.8	3.9	20.0	20.2	274	64	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
2.	3	47.0	47.2	4.1	4.4	19.3	19.0	122	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
3.	4	48.2	48.5	4.4	4.2	18.7	18.4	231	50	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
4.	5	49.3	49.1	4.7	4.4	18.2	18.3	228	63	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
5.	6	50.4	50.7	5.0	4.9	17.6	17.3	265	65	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
6.	7	51.4	51.6	5.3	5.1	17.1	16.8	132	46	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
7.	8	52.3	52.5	5.5	5.6	16.6	16.3	307-308(d)	52	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
8.	9	53.2	53.5	5.7	5.9	16.2	15.9	109	43	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
9.	10	54.1	54.3	6.0	5.9	15.8	15.9	322(d)	70	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
10.	12	55.7	55.8	6.4	6.2	15.0	14.9	210	75	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂

All the melting points are uncorrected and the compounds were recrystallised from water. (d) = decomposed.

TABLE 2

Test compound	<i>n</i> as in 1	No. of animals	Initial blood sugar (mg/100 ml)	Blood sugar (mg/100 ml) level after	
				1 hr	3 hr
Control	x	3	101.94 ± 5.2*	99.86 ± 4.5	98.68 ± 5.2
1	2	3	100.79 ± 0.86	88.71 ± 2.25	69.02 ± 1.46
2	3	3	93.75 ± 1.63	75.08 ± 1.46	73.32 ± 1.40
3	6	3	93.22 ± 2.42	94.76 ± 2.21	76.25 ± 9.65
4	7	3	92.59 ± 0.74	72.78 ± 10.68	76.79 ± 7.24
5	8	3	95.09 ± 2.50	91.38 ± 3.19	77.01 ± 4.51
6	9	3	85.89 ± 2.66	80.11 ± 0.14	64.67 ± 12.07
7	10	3	94.77 ± 0.84	82.58 ± 6.30	65.70 ± 6.36
8	12	3	95.54 ± 8.37	103.48 ± 2.50	67.73 ± 5.42
Tolbutamide	—	5	87.12 ± 14.00	69.95 ± 13.12	52.36 ± 15.90

* Mean ± Standard error.

150-200 g fasted for 18 hr. (water was allowed ad. lib.).

The blood sugar was determined by collection of blood from the tail of the rats and determined by the method of Folin and Wu⁹.

A suspension of 250 mg/kg of the test compounds in gum acacia was administered orally to ten groups of rats. The blood sugar was determined after 1 and 3 hr. All of the test drugs and the reference drug, tolbutamide were administered at 250 mg/kg. Preliminary results are reported in Table 2.

It may be noted that compounds with *n* = 2, 10 and 12 (as in 1) are showing high activity under conditions at which tolbutamide is known to exhibit hypoglycemic activity.

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References

1. E. FRANK, M. NOTHMANN and A. WAGNER, *Klin. Wochschr.*, 1926, 5, 2100.
2. E. FRANK, *Naturwiss.*, 1927, 15, 213.

3. I. SIMON, *Bull. Soc. Ital. Biol. Sper.*, 1956, 32, 1329.
4. H. RUSCHIG, G. KORGER, W. AUMULIER, H. WAGNER, R. WEYER, A. BANDER and J. SCHOLZ, *Arzneimittel-Forsch.*, 1958, 8, 448.
5. K. OKAMATO, T. TAIL, H. KOSO, N. TAKENAKA, T. HAYAKAWA and T. IBARAKI; *Tohoku. J. Exptl. Med.*, 1955, 61, (Suppl. 3), 36.
6. S. M. DESPANDE, K. C. DATTA, A. K. SANYAL and M. K. RAJNA; *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, 1, 143.
7. J. A. VAN ALLAN and B. D. DEACON, "Organic Syntheses", Coll. Vol. IV., J. Wiley and Sons Inc., New York, N.Y. 1963, p. 569.
8. R. O. ROBLIN JR. and J. W. CLAPP, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4890.
9. O. FOLIN and H. WU, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1920, 41, 367.

Thermal Synthesis of Glycozoline

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RECENTLY diphenylamine (I) has been shown to cyclise to carbazole¹ (II) under thermal condition at a temperature of 350° in presence of trace amounts of iodine as catalyst. The method was extended to the synthesis of glycozolidine¹, C₁₅H₁₅NO₂ (III), m.p. 160°-62°, a carbazole alkaloid of *Glycosmis pentaphylla*. We now report a new synthesis of glycozoline^{2,3}, C₁₄H₁₃NO (IV) m.p. 181°-82°, a